
COST OF PEACE ACCOUNTING ON FOREIGN DIRECT INVESTMENT IN NIGERIA

BY

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Abstract: *This study examined the cost of peace accounting on foreign direct investment in Nigeria, a time series dataset was developed by the researcher from the information provided by CBN Statistical Bulletin from 2013-2022. The analysis was performed via the STATA 14.0 version from which the ordinary least-squares regression shows an absent of autocorrelation, that is no serial correlation. Contrary, to the assumption that error that is uncorrelated or independent for time series data is often not appropriate. The method described by Cochrane and Orcutt (1949) was employed in the work thereby clearly showing that the regression line fits the data and Durbin Watson (Dw) suggests that the model is serially correlated since 1.578646 lies between the autocorrelation critical value of 1.5 to 2.0. The study observed that the Nigeria Federal government spending on security has negative and insignificant relationship on the inflow of foreign direct investment, signifying that it was not improving the inflow of FDI during the period of investigation. Based on the findings, the study recommends among others that the government should provide an enabling environment that will encourage foreign investors to invest in Nigeria economy by addressing the security challenges in the country, providing investment friendly environment by improved regulatory framework as well as encourage domestic investment.*

Keywords: Peace accounting, National security, Foreign Direct Investment, Gross Domestic Product.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Insecurity in Nigeria has become very high to the extent that kidnapping and requesting for a huge sum of ransom by Boko Harams, then gruesome murdering of the victims after the huge sum have been paid which is incessant in the Northern part of Nigeria and have escalated to the Eastern and Western region constitutes great challenges and threat to both the peaceful co-existence and economic property of the country. Nigeria has joined the group of countries that spend a higher proportion of their budgetary allocation on security. There is no opposition that the huge resources (both human and materials) that would have had alternative uses were expended profusely to achieve peace in those regions and intensify peace locally.

The role Foreign Direct Investment as an engine of accelerating economic growth and development in developing economies like Nigeria cannot be overemphasized. The underdeveloped nature of the Nigerian economy that essentially hindered the pace of her economic development has necessitated the demand for foreign direct investment into the country (Ugwuegbe, Okore and John, 2013). Generally, no business or enterprise can thrive in tense and insecure environment. This has serious implication for foreign direct investment and economic development. Civil war, terrorism and social unrest will not only result in uncertainty in the investment and financial environment but also increase security expenses, leading to poor output and retard productive capacity, reduce foreign direct investment benefits, damages properties, infrastructures and displacement of both direct and indirect foreign investment which has serious impact on the economic growth and development of emerging economies, (Adeyeye, Ayodele and Akinuli, 2016). The sour happenings in this country ranging from losses of infrastructural, human lives and properties had repelled the inflow of foreign direct investment which contributes significantly to the Gross Domestic Product of Nigeria. Needless to say that foreign direct investment has significant contribution to the economic growth in terms of the introduction of modern science, technology and organization and many other countless benefits. Foreign Direct Investment encourages entrepreneurs to invest and gives room for cordial relationship among the countries involves, (Adeyeye et al 2016).

Nigeria as a nation is faced with numerous security challenges, these challenges has threatened both the growth and peaceful co-existence of lives, thus achieving peace has remained a difficult task for the past and successive government. This work assesses the relationship between cost of peace accounting and foreign direct investment in Nigeria; thereby trying to answer the questions, does the budget allocation to security forces guarantee peace and serenity which the good citizens of Nigeria crave for and, do foreigners feel secured in the country?

2.0 REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

This section will be devoted to the review of related literature. The literature emanates in two forms: conceptual framework and empirical review

2.1 Conceptual framework

Peace Accounting: The cost of ensuring national security is very high, but measuring this cost has received little attention. One way of recording and ascertaining the financial resources expended on national security is via "Peace Accounting". According to Okoro and Egbunike, (2016), Peace accounting can be seen as the process of recording, analyzing and providing of information that relates to cost of curtailing violence or cost associated with peace-keeping.

They opined that these pieces of information are so important that it solves the agency problem that may erupt between the government and the citizens. One of the major problems in peace accounting, according to them, is the failure of the agent (government) to meet disclosure requirements concerning utilization of state's resources in prosecuting different peacekeeping operations. The government is also reluctant in disclosing destruction of assets (especially human capital assets) of the state. Perhaps, the agent engages in this act in order not to instill fear and panic into the citizenry without consideration of the consequences such distortions pose to the accounting process. To that effect, Stiglitz and Bilmes (2012), asserts that the only way to mitigate the agency problem is through transparency. Peace-accounting brings about information that may instill transparency that can be passed from the principal (citizens) and its agent (government).

Udeh, Ugwu and Odo (2017) see peace accounting as being pervasive. They argue that it goes beyond recording, analyzing, summarizing and interpreting costs associated with curtailing violence or peace-keeping. It includes costs of negotiations, compromises and sacrifices made by government and groups of people to ensure the existence of positive peace in a locality. Thereby defining peace accounting as the art of recording, analyzing, summarizing, interpreting and communicating costs associated with prevention of violence, peace - keeping, negotiations and compromises made towards institution and maintenance of positive peace in a locality.

In summary, we say that peace accounting is a technique of gathering, recording, analyzing, summarizing, interpreting, disclosing and communicating to the principal accordingly, unbiased information relating to the cost of mitigating violence, peace-keeping and other forms of insecurity, thereby maintaining positive peace in a locality.

Foreign Direct Investment (FDI)

Foreign direct investment (FDI) is the process whereby residents of one country (the source country) acquire ownership of assets for the purpose of controlling the production and other activities of a firm in another country (the host country), (Mohammad, Muhammad & Li, 2013).

There are several forms through which Foreign Direct Investment could flow into a country. It could come in form of subsidiary of a multinational company or in form of merger and acquisition with a local firm in the host country. It could come in form of creation of non-current assets in the other country by the national of the investing country (Obadan, 2004). In this kind of investment, the Multinational firm exercises de facto or de jure authority over the assets they have formed. One major reason an investor acquires asset in a foreign country is to establish its physical presence in that country and thus exercises lasting control in the management of the enterprise wherein the direct investment evolves.

Falki (2009), speaking on the effects and advantages of FDI to the host economy, noted that the effects of FDI on the host economy are normally believed to be: increase in employment, augmenting the productivity, boost in exports and amplified pace of transfer of technology. The potential advantages of the FDI to the host economy are: it facilitates the utilization and exploitation of local raw materials, introduces modern techniques of management and marketing, ease the access to new technologies, foreign inflows can be used for financing current account deficits.

Impact of Foreign Direct Investment on economic growth in Nigeria

Foreign Direct Investment is an investment made to acquire a lasting management interest (normally 10% of voting stock) in a business enterprise operating in a country other than that

of the investor defined according to residency (World Bank, 1996). Such investments may take the form of either “greenfield” investment (also called “mortar and brick” investment) or merger and acquisition (M&A), which entails the acquisition of existing interest rather than new investment. FDI comprises not only merger and acquisition and new investment, but also reinvested earnings and loans and similar capital transfer between parent companies and their affiliates. Countries could be both host to FDI projects in their own country and a participant in investment projects in other countries. A country’s inward FDI position is made up of the hosted FDI projects, while outward FDI comprises those investment projects owned abroad, (Adeolu, 2007).

Foreign Direct Investment and Cost of Peace Accounting

Insecurity and terrorism have a huge economic, socio and physical cost. It is obvious that the loss of human lives and the suffering of survivors in the aftermath of an attack can be tremendous. Apart from the loss of lives, terrorist attacks are likely to have negative consequences on the investment behavior (Montclair Kimberley Academy, 2005). Withdrawal of Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) by countries and companies may occur due to the direct destruction of infrastructure, the rise of operational costs as a result of high demand for security (Frey, Lvechinger & Stutzer, 2007).

According to Andyopadhyay, Sandler and Younas (2011) the economic dimension of terrorism concerns losses in Foreign Direct Investment (FDI), damaged infrastructure, output losses, security costs, reduced economic growth, reduced tourism, trade losses, higher insurance premiums, and longer waits in airports (Keefer and Loayza, 2008). Terrorist are well aware of the potential economic harms that their attacks can cause and view these consequences as pressuring besieged government to concede to their demand. A country (developing nation like Nigeria) plagued with an intense long-term terrorist campaign can suffer significant losses in Gross Domestic Product (GDP), Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) and Gross Domestic Product Growth (GDPG) (Abadie & Gardeazabal, 2003).

Insecurity may also direct economic resources from highly productive sectors to less productive sectors thereby crowding out investment. No meaningful growth and development can take place in the continuous face of insecurity. It will not only reduce GDP and fuel inflation but also the flows of foreign direct investment (Owolabi & Ayenakin, 2015).

2.2 Theoretical Framework:

The two commonly applied theories in peace accounting are the accounting and economic theories. The accounting theory in the views of Jurgen and Paul (2010) is concerned with the total value of damaged assets such as physical, human and social capital in a fiscal period. On the other hand, Stiglitz and Bilmes (2012) state that economic theory deals with macro-economic implications coming from the amount of money spent on domestic investment due to violence. In as much as these theories capture significant aspects of peace accounting, they paid little or no attention to the preventive measures of conflicts.

Ury, Brett and Goldberg's theory (1993) expressed in Asuquo, Dickson, Emechebe & Uduma (2016), canvasses for reduction in the cost of preventing, managing and settling disputes. Specifically, they examined power, right and interest-based methods of dispute resolution. They assert that in the power-based method of conflicts resolution, the parties’ resort to the use of coercion. They see this option as a first-line measure where one of the parties is considered an under-dog. Unfortunately, one of the major limitations of this option is that it may succeed in suppressing an agitated group temporarily but it does not produce a permanent resolution of conflicts. Again, Ury, et al (1993) contend that whenever parties in a

conflict seek resolution through the application of rules, rights and principles, the right based method is in vogue. Sometimes, rights referred to in this case could be those reached by collective agreement or through a legislature procedure. Lastly, they identified interest-based method as a joint problem-solving technique that combines facilitation and mediation. They believe that this method is less cost-effective as it is more robust than other methods. They are however, of the opinion that a hybrid of interest and right based methods will produce a more acceptable dispute resolution results.

In our own view, none of the above theories is adequate to comprehensively address peace accounting in an evolving society like ours. We therefore, advocate an integrative peace accounting theory that combines costs associated with prevention of conflicts and the accounting theory. While the accounting theory takes care of total value of assets damaged during violence, the preventive theory captures all expenses and sacrifices made by various federating units to give them a sense of belonging to the national entity and consequently prevent agitation. As a result of the above, this paper is anchored on the integrative peace accounting theory.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

The study employed ex-post facto research design in its methodology while it extracted secondary data from Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Statistical Bulletin (2022) for a period of 10 years from 2013-2022. This study investigates the relationship between Cost of Peace Accounting and Foreign Direct Investment. The peace accounting costs were proxied by expenditure on internal security and expenditure on defense because insecurity cannot be captured in quantitative term. Expenditure on internal security is costs associated with insecurity, political violence, insurgency, militancy, economic predicament, corruption, Gross Domestic Product stood for economic growth in Nigeria as expressed in Owolabi & Ayenakin (2015).

The model used in this research work is based on Adeyeye, Ayodele & Akinuli (2016). They investigated the Impact of Security Expenditure on Foreign Direct Investment in Nigeria linkage between Security Expenditure and Foreign Direct Investment. Their model specified that Security Expenditure (proxied by Expenditure on Internal Security and Expenditure on Defence) is significantly influenced by Foreign Direct Investment.

In this study, the model with be;

$$FDI = \beta_0 + \beta_1 EINTS + \beta_2 EDF + \beta_3 GDP + \epsilon_t$$

Where:

FDI = Foreign Direct Investment

EINTS = Expenditure on Internal Security

EDF = Expenditure on Defence

GDP = Gross Domestic Product

B = beta is constant

ϵ = error term.

As stated in the model, the variables include Foreign Direct Investment (FDI), which is taken as the dependent variable; EINTS, EDF, and GDP are the independent variables.

4.0 RESULTS

A time series dataset was developed by the researcher from the information provided by CBN Statistical Bulletin. The analysis was performed via the STATA 14.0 version from which the ordinary least-squares regression shows an absent of autocorrelation, that is no serial

correlation. Contrary to the assumption that error that is uncorrelated or independent for time series data is often not appropriate. Usually, the errors in time series data exhibit serial correlation, that is, such error terms are said to be autocorrelated. Autocorrelation is a mathematical representation of the degree of similarity between a given time series and a lagged version of itself over a successive time interval. It measures the relationship between a variable's value and its past value, (Tim Smith, 2020). When the apparent autocorrelation in the errors cannot be removed by adding one or more new regressors to the model, it is necessary to explicitly recognize the autocorrelative structure in the model and devise an appropriate parameter estimation method. There are a number of estimation procedures that can be used. The method described by Cochrane and Orcutt (1949) was employed in this work and this clearly shows that the regression line fits the data and Durbin Watson (Dw) suggests that the model is serially correlated since 1.578646 lies between the autocorrelation critical value of 1.5 to 2.0.

Table 1: Summary of Cochrane-Orcutt AR(1) regression -- iterated estimates

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• tsset year
  time variable: year, 2013 to 2022
    delta: 1 unit

• Cochrane-Orcutt AR(1) regression -- iterated estimates
-----+-----
Source |      SS      df      MS      Number of obs   =      18
-----+-----
Model |  .467942313      3  .155980771  F(3, 14)         =      7.96
Residual |  .274250787     14  .019589342  Prob > F         =      0.0024
-----+-----
Total |  .7421931      17  .043658418  R-squared        =      0.6305
Adj R-squared =      0.5513
Root MSE   =      .13996

-----+-----
      fdi |      Coef.   Std. Err.      t    P>|t|     [95% Conf. Interval]
-----+-----
eints |  -.293277   .3768958    -0.78  0.449    -1.101638   .5150842
edf   |  -.5708697  .225722    -2.53  0.024    -1.054995  -.0867443
gdp   |  1.539675   .3992318     3.86  0.002     .6834084   2.395942
_cons |  7.755506   .440174    17.62  0.000     6.811426   8.699585

-----+-----
rho   |  .2490663

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Durbin-Watson statistic (original)    1.396134
Durbin-Watson statistic (transformed) 1.578646
Source: Authors' Computation, 2025
    
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Table 1 shows the correlation analysis between Peace Accounting Costs indices and FDI. From the findings, it can be observed that the independent variable EDF has a significant and negative relationship with FDI inflow, at the (P<0.05) level of significance (0.024) and a negative coefficient of (-0.5708697), this implies that a unit decrease in EDF leads to a decrease in FDI by -0.5708697 unit. The regression result shows that GDP has a positive and statistically significant relationship with FDI inflow, at the (P<0.05) level of significant (0.002) and a positive coefficient of (1.539675), this implies that a unit increase in EDF leads to an increase in FDI by 1.539675 unit. Although, this is not the same with the findings of EINTS, which has a negative relationship with foreign direct investment (FDI), and is insignificantly different from (P<0.05) level of significance. This shows that the Nigeria Federal government spending on security has negative and insignificant relationship on the

inflow of foreign direct investment, signifying that it was not improving the inflow of FDI during the period of investigation.

5.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Looking at this result, we conclude that expenditure on internal security has a negative and insignificant relationship on the inflow of foreign direct investment. It was also observed that insecurity discourages foreign direct investment in Nigeria, therefore, government should provide an enabling environment that will encourage foreign investors to invest in Nigeria economy by addressing the security challenges in the country, providing investment friendly environment by improved regulatory framework as well as encourage domestic investment. This problem should be addressed promptly squarely by the government and other stakeholders if Nigeria will continue to compete favorably in the global fund market. Notably, it is the growth in the domestic economy that attracted the inflow of FDI into the Nigeria economy for the period under consideration. This is based on the understanding that an economy with a potential for providing higher return on investment will attract more foreign investors as they (foreign investors) prefer to invest in an area that promises higher returns on investment.

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APPENDIX

Table-1. Expenditure on Internal Security, (EINTS) and Expenditure on Defense (in N.M) FDI & GDP in Nigeria 2013 to 2022.

YEAR	FDI	EINTS	EDF	GDP
2013	9.78004585	2.350629001	2.298221	2.560337
2014	9.946506956	2.447158031	2.452093	2.613138
2015	9.849415372	2.559308011	2.472464	2.662168
2016	9.745299192	2.46648283	2.435088	2.711779
2017	9.67152723	2.436387292	2.438591	2.75473
2018	9.486312701	2.612995656	2.51929	2.694239
2019	9.648236333	2.620825055	2.579973	2.607079
2020	9.54444003	2.599829463	2.558617	2.574894
2021	9.300483563	2.689886779	2.645571	2.600058
2022	9.302190954	2.825188347	2.770107	2.651395